

Farmer Clusters Matter: How Farmer Cluster can enhance participation in Agri-environmental Contracts

The policy brief explores different agri-environment contract designs in the United Kingdom, France, and the Netherlands (Fritschle et al., forthcoming).

Policy recommendations

1. Accompanying AECS implementation with the setting up of farmer clusters, thereby allowing farmers **to exchange with peers** to coordinate conservation efforts on a landscape scale, can increase their participation in AE contracts.
2. **Setting up farmer clusters at a larger scale**, extending the FRAMEwork advanced farmer clusters, to investigate on a more solid empirical basis how farmers react to collaborative landscape-scale conservation approaches.
3. Connecting and **supporting the establishment of optional collaborative farmer groups**, such as farmer clusters, may help make AE contracts more attractive to farmers.

Agri-environmental Schemes and the Farmer Cluster Approach

In the EU and the UK, farmers seeking to enhance farmland biodiversity and preserve ecosystems can access agri-environmental contracts (AEC) offered by both private entities (such as NGOs or companies) and public, governmental bodies. These contracts provide financial support for adopting and implementing sustainable farming practices. Public agri-environmental contracts (AEC), known as agri-environmental schemes, are a key component of the EU Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). However, the CAP has faced criticism for not meeting its sustainability goals, thus impeding progress towards more sustainable food production and biodiversity conservation in Europe (Pe'er et al., 2020).

Several factors contribute to the shortcomings of AEC and their inability to effectively halt biodiversity loss. For example, the low participation rate of farmers in voluntary AEC hampers the efficient implementation of sustainable farming practices. This low participation suggests that many available contracts do not adequately address the needs of European farmers. Additionally, while conservation goals such as enhancing biodiversity through habitat conservation are more effective at the landscape scale, standard AEC primarily focus on farm-level management of ecosystem services (Pe'er et al., 2020).

Incorporating collective elements, like Farmer Clusters, into AEC design offers the potential for more effective landscape-scale conservation by extending beyond the traditional farm-level approach (Pe'er et al., 2022). However, new design elements, such as the Farmer Cluster approach, should be

Advanced Farmer Clusters

Farmer Clusters are farmer-led groups. The groups are supported by facilitators, who support farmers with administrative and conservation-related aspects. Member of farmer clusters can exchange knowledge with other farmers and coordinate their efforts to improve biodiversity and other ecosystem services at the landscape rather than the farm level (Nye, 2018 and Bohnet et al., 2025). The FRAMEwork project includes 11 **Farmer Clusters** from 9 European countries (Bohnet, I. et al. 2025).

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thoroughly evaluated before being integrated into AEC, as their design is crucial for farmer enrolment (Fritschle et al., 2022; Canessa et al., 2024; Schaller et al., 2022 and Schulze et al., 2023). Therefore, we investigated whether introducing the Farmer Cluster approach into AEC could boost farmers' enrolment rates.

Evaluating Farmer Preferences for Biodiversity-Sensitive Agri-Environmental Schemes

To evaluate preferences for new agri-environmental contract designs aimed at biodiversity-sensitive farming, a discrete choice experiment (DCE) was conducted. This method allows researchers to assess farmers' preferences for different contract designs in a controlled setting (Colen et al., 2016). In the study, farmers in France, the UK and the Netherlands were presented with descriptions of several hypothetical 5-year agri-environmental contracts, all requiring six-meter-wide field margins around arable fields and asked to choose their preferred option (Fritschle et al., forthcoming). Each respondent faced six choice situations, each with two different hypothetical contracts (Programme A or Programme B) and the option to remain in their current situation. The contracts varied in four characteristics: the source of funding, payment methods, collective components (Farmer Clusters), and the expected payment per hectare of field margin per year. The choices made by farmers were used to estimate the importance of these contract characteristics.

Results

According to farmers, who should organise the agri-environmental contract?

On average, farmers in our sample prefer AEC organised by the government over those organised by retail companies or NGOs.

Do farmers prefer a particular method of payment for their efforts?

On average, farmers in our sample prefer AEC offering a per-hectare payment over those offering a price premium that they would receive through selling labelled produce.

How do farmers perceive agri-environmental contracts with associated farmer groups?

On average, farmers prefer AEC that grant them the option to join a Farmer Cluster compared to schemes with no Farmer Cluster or schemes with mandatory Farmer Cluster participation.

Do the findings apply to all farmers in the sample?

No, not all farmers prefer the same types of schemes. We find significant heterogeneity in farmers' preferences for the organiser and the compensation method.

1. **Organiser:** A small group of 166 farmers (21.8%) in the sample prefer contracts organised by NGOs over contracts organised by the government. Another small group of 141 farmers (18.5%) prefer contracts organised by retailers over schemes organised by the government. The country of origin can explain part of the heterogeneity. Compared to Dutch farmers, French and UK farmers seem not to show preferences for a particular organiser. Compared to farmers from France and the UK, Dutch farmers seem to prefer contracts organised by retailers less than government contracts.
2. **Compensation method:** A small group of 93 farmers (12.2%) in the sample prefer contracts providing payment through a price premium associated with a label more than contracts paying through a per-hectare payment. The farmers' country of origin does not explain whether the per-hectare payment or the label is preferred.
3. **Farmer clusters:** Nearly all farmers in the sample (758 of 761 or 99.6%) prefer the option to join a Farmer Cluster, while all farmers (761) also dislike being forced to join a Farmer Cluster.

Policy Implications

1. **Establishing Farmer Clusters alongside agri-environmental contracts will likely increase participation as long as it is optional.**
2. **A one-size-fits-all agri-environmental contracts to incentivise biodiversity-sensitive farming does not seem appropriate.**

Farmers' preferences for AEC attributes differ a lot. However, we know what contract the majority of farmers in our sample would prefer: namely AEC with per-hectare payments, organised by the government, with an option to join a Farmer Cluster.

Further Readings

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15090425>

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In preparation

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